

9. X-ray Powder File, Stam, Inorganic Set 1 to 10.
10. S. F. WEST and C. F. AUDRIETH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 1069.
11. A. G. SCROGGIE and G. L. CLARK, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.* 1925, **15**, 1.

Synthesis of Some New Heteropoly Salts

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IN this communication three distinctly new heteropoly salts of molybdenum, vanadium and tungsten with 1:6, central:condensing atom ratio are reported.

The conditions of formations are the same as has been discussed in the previous communications^{1,2}. The pH were maintained rigorously throughout the experiment.

6-Sodium tungstomanganate :

50 ml of .2M sodium tungstate, 45 ml of 0.05M manganese sulphate and 14 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed together (pH 3.64), stirred vigorously for one hour, kept in a steam bath for three hours and left for crystallisation. Greyish white powdery compound was collected after an interval of seven days. The compound was analysed chemically and colorimetrically : (Found : Mn, 2.21 ; W, 48.23 ; Na, 1.00 ; H 2.25 ; calcd. for $\text{Na}_{10}[\text{MnW}_6\text{O}_{24}]28\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Mn, 2.41 ; W, 48.48 ; Na, 1.10 ; H, 2.45 per cent).

6-Ammonium molybdochromate :

Solutions of 50 ml of 0.05M ammonium molybdate, 40 ml of .05M potassium dichromate and 20 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed together rapidly at pH 2.8, digested for three hours, evaporated to crystallisation on a water bath and left overnight ; orange coloured flaky powdery compound was separated after an interval of five days. From analysis : (Found : Cr, 4.02 ; Mo, 46.72 ; N, 6.62 ; H, 3.32 ; calcd. for : $(\text{NH}_4)_6[\text{CrMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]10\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cr, 4.22 ; Mo, 46.90 ; N, 6.68 ; H, 3.58 ; per cent).

6-Potassium vanadochromate :

Solutions of 50 ml of .013M ammonium metavanadate, 43 ml of .05M potassium dichromate and 14 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed by constant stirring (pH 2.4) for half an hour, digested for two hours and crystallised on a steam bath. After an interval of ten days brick-red shining crystals were collected from analysis : (Found : Cr, 5.22 ; V, 31.83 ; K, 8.03 ; H, 2.31 ; calcd. for $\text{K}_2[\text{CrV}_6\text{O}_{19}]12\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cr, 5.43 ; V, 32.00 ; K, 8.15 ; H, 2.51 per cent).

References

1. H. C. MISHRA, S. K. ROY and A. N. OJHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 307.
2. S. K. ROY and G. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 638 ; 1975, **52**, 1152.

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Bipositive Cations with 6-Mercaptopurine and Thioguanine in Solution

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6-MERCAPTOPURINE (MCP) and 2-amino-6-mercaptopurine (thioguanine, TGN) have been introduced in human cancer therapy, and has proved effective as anticancer agent in comparison to other purine derivatives like adenine and TGN. MCP and TGN having similar structures, form chelates with metal ions, which probably determine their activities.

The present communication deals with attempts to study mixed complexes of MCP and TGN with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II), using 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) or 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) as primary ligands. Studies with Cu(II) and Zn(II) were not possible.

Chelating reactions between the above metal ions and MCP have been described by Freiser *et al*¹, while TGN complexes with Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Pb(II), UO₂(VI), Ca(II) and Mg(II) have been reported earlier². Formation constants of the mixed complexes have been determined using a modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration technique^{3,4}.

Experimental

All materials used were of reagent grade. Stock solutions (0.01M) of phen and bipy were prepared in water. 0.01M solutions of MCP and TGN were freshly prepared by dissolving in 0.02M alkali. Solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardized against EDTA⁵.

pH measurements were done using an Elico pH meter (model LI-10) with glass (EK-62A) and calomel electrodes. The pH meter was calibrated with 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate solution.

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